

A Study on the Nostalgia Contents Analysis of Hometown Alumni in the Online Community

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Abstract— This study aims to analyze the text terms posted on an online community of people from the same hometown and to understand the topic and trend of nostalgia composed online. For this purpose, this study collected 144 writings which the natives of Yeongjong Island, Incheon, South-Korea have posted on an online community. And it analyzed association relations. As a result, online community texts means that just defining nostalgia as 'a mind longing for hometown' is not an enough explanation. Second, texts composed online have abstractness rather than persons' individual stories. This study figured out the relationship that had the most critical and closest mutual association among the terms that constituted nostalgia through literature research and association rule concerning nostalgia. The result of this study has a characteristic that it summed up the core terms and emotions related to nostalgia.

Keywords—Nostalgia, cultural memory, data mining, online community.

I. INTRODUCTION

RECENTLY, 'Nostalgia' has been attracting attention as a main keyword and content of popular culture. Especially, the nostalgia of the retro style is popular in various parts such as the advertisement and the brand as well as the drama drawn with the past when it was delightful and happy. The masses who consume this nostalgia reach their nostalgia through culturally commodified nostalgia. In other words, as a cultural keyword, Nostalgia redefines an individual's nostalgia reflecting the times and culture we are experiencing today.

For Koreans in their 50s and older who have experienced urbanization and industrialization in Korea, nostalgia has the opposite meaning. Their nostalgia is characterized by their reflection on themselves, their interactivity with past residents, playfulness that reproduces past work as play, and everydayness reproduced as trivial things in everyday life rather than special events [1]. For them, nostalgia is a longing for a physical and empirical place of the past, a new force for living the present and future, and a driving force for changing the future.

The main way in which they spent and reproduced nostalgia was face-to-face meetings. But recently this form has changed dramatically. The development and dissemination of digital

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media is changing the expression and circulation of emotions while expanding human emotion from analog space to digital space. Those in their early 50s and early 60s are digital immigrants who have adapted to the digital environment that began in earnest in the 2000s but still have a great analog character. However, when they are in their 30s and 40s, they have experience using alumni-gathering Internet sites such as *I Love School* or *Damoim* (means altogether). And recently, it is a generation that actively uses SNS such as *Facebook*, *Kakao Talk* and *Naver band*. The more they actively adapt to the digital environment, the more often their emotions and memories are depicted in the online space rather than the face-to-face situations of the past.

The purpose of this study is to analyze and visualize the story of nostalgia implemented in online community. Nostalgia, the universal sensibility of Korean society, can be identified through the relationship of words that signify nostalgia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

The birth of the hometown brought to modern times soon leads to the creation of the concept of Nostalgia. Nostalgia, meaning nostalgia in the West, is a compound word for 'nostos' meaning returning home and 'algos' meaning painful condition. Nostalgia was first used in 1678 by Swiss physician Johannes Hofer in his treatise, "imaginary suffering" from "a desire to return to his hometown" in the name of nostalgia. Nostalgia has been used as a 'disease name' as a nostalgia for his motherland and hometown as a kind of obsession that affects the physical body [2]. Nostalgia has been accepted as a universal experience and emotion that transcends "disease" only after 1900 and transcends certain persons such as soldiers and immigrants who originate in time and space.

Nostalgia is expressed through the process of 'sense-memory-story'. Certain stimuli find a rhythm of existence from the senses, while at the same time the rhythm changes to the form of existence and reconstructs or recreates the hometown world. In other words, the nostalgia experienced at the dimension of sense starts with a special stimulus such as physical stimulation or event such as seeing or hearing. This nostalgia is expressed and expressed in narrative across the space of memory.

Constructs that make up memories - the continuity and transformation of images and narratives are related to their moral status or current purpose. Especially, collective memory acts have a meaning in the moral order - mythical level in essence. This memory is not related to a priori structure. According to Bakhtin's expression, all memory is a process of continuous utterance and response, so it does not remain as a

fixed form or justice but develops with new meaning and usefulness as it has been used for many years. According to Halbwachs, "People usually get memories in society. Also, people recollect, recognize and materialize memories in society." Thus, memory is an indicator of social differentiation. However, this does not mean that the memory of the individual is composed solely of societies. No matter how memories are organized in social frameworks and identities, memories are personal because memory is ultimately a personal act [3]. This nostalgia is a combination of personal experience and the image of the home in a personal and social context.

III. METHODS

A. Research Objects

To collect nostalgia stories, this study analyzed the articles of online trends. The online community which is the study subject of this study is the *Daum* online community which is called 'the beautiful *Yeongjong zigi*' (*zigi* means friend). This is a community where people who are in the *Yeongjong* area are joined and active. In order to join this community, you have to bear the evidence that you put your *Yeongjong* area in your home. The proof is that the recommendation of the existing community members who can prove the name of the person who graduated from elementary, middle and high school and the home of the new member need.

The total number of members of this online community is 150, with 30 visitors per day. The major age of members is from the late 50s to the early 60s and consists of a total of 24 menus. Among these menus, the menu that writes about the hometown and perfume is 'Story of life & my own work'. This menu is a bulletin board to post the thoughts, emotions, and the stories of the past that come to mind in daily life, unlike the free bulletin board where "interesting" oriented articles are posted. Mainly text stories are posted and occasionally pictures or images are posted together. However, since the number of photographs and images is very insignificant compared to the whole text, only texts are studied in this study. The analysis period is from January 01, 2016 to December 31, 2016 for one year. A total of 144 text data were filtered based on these criteria.

B. Analysis Tools and Procedures

1. Data Collection and Processing

A total of 151 articles were collected from January 01, 2016 to December 31, 2016. Of these, 12 texts that were judged not to match the nature of the bulletin board were excluded from the text data of this study. The text posted in the community was converted to a Windows Notepad file (*.txt). The text data collected for each month are shown in Table I. The data shown in Table I was processed through text processing. First, symbols, numbers, spaces, etc. were removed or segmented by meaning. Based on the above data, the following data analysis sets were also processed.

2. Correlation Analysis

Association Rule, a technique of data mining, refers to an

analytical method that groups the items with high relevance by measuring the degree of association of items from data and visually shows the relationship between them [4], [5]. In other words, it is useful when you want to find the rules of the form $X \rightarrow Y$ by showing which items are accompanied by other items [6]. In this study, we used *arules* (association rules) package and *arulesViz* (visualizing association rules) package for correlation analysis.

TABLE I
 MONTHLY QUANTITY OF COLLECTED DATA

Duration	Data	Duration	Data
Jan	13	Jul	11
Feb	13	Aug	13
Mar	10	Sept	18
Apr	7	Oct	10
May	21	Nov	11
Jun	12	Dec	12

IV. RESULTS

In this study, we analyzed the relationship between texts, key terms, and morphemes to understand the status of online nostalgia. This is to visualize the association rules between terms in the data and to quantify the rule-frequency, relationship, etc. in which each term occurs. The association analysis of the data was performed according to the following Table II.

TABLE II
 RESEARCH FIGURE

	Confidence	Support	Lift
Figure	0.4	0.06	2

As a result of the association analysis, it can be seen that the one having the most connection with the other terms constituting the nostalgia is the 'mind'. 'Mind' was linked to 'healthy', 'season', 'laugh', 'gorgeous', 'phone call', 'cold', 'warm', 'life', 'stimulus', 'sea'. This means that the term 'thinking' appears when the term 'healthy' appears, and the term 'sunlight' is linked to the term 'cold', which again refers to the term 'mind'. In addition to this, it turns out that the words 'thinking', 'today' and 'mind' have a subordinate relationship with other words. In the text, the word 'thinking' appears when the terms 'longing', 'meeting', 'moment', 'precious', 'season', 'coffee' has emerged. This may be a connected word such as an unhappy mind, a sudden meeting, a nostalgic mind, but it also means that the term 'inconvenience' has appeared in the specific text B, written by online community user A. This result can be expressed as shown in Fig. 1.

V. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study is to analyze and understand the topics and trends on online nostalgia by analyzing the text terms posted on the online trend community. The main results of the study are summarized as follows.

First, visualization results through association analysis are as follows. Through the visualization, which is a set of texts to be

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